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Experimental

$K_2[Zn(Etxant)_4]$ or $K_2[Cd(Etxant)_4]$ required for the synthesis of $MM'(Etxant)_4$ were prepared *in situ* in methanol-water mixtures as described previously¹⁻³. To the above Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} tetraxanthate solution $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Pb(NO_3)_2$, $AgNO_3$, $VO_2SO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ or Tl_2SO_4 dissolved in the same solvent mixture was added in 1 : 1/1 : 2 molar ratios. The heterobimetallic xanthates thus precipitated were filtered, washed with methanol-water mixture and dried in vacuum.

The experimental details pertaining to analysis, magnetic susceptibility, molar conductance, electronic and infrared spectral measurements were the same as described in our previous papers^{1,2}. The relevant analytical data are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data show the formation of heterobimetallic compounds of the general formula $MM'(Etxant)_4$. The compounds do not melt but decompose in the temperature range 122–170°, and all are insoluble in water and common organic solvents except $VOZn(Etxant)_4$ and $VOCd(Etxant)_4$ which are slightly soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide. The insolubility of the complexes and their non-melting nature suggest their polymeric nature and this has precluded the determination of their molar conductance and molecular weights. The low values of molar conductance⁵ (2.34–4.6 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) for the oxovanadium(II) compounds indicate that they are non-ionic. The μ_{eff} values (1.69–1.74 B.M.) for $VOZn(Etxant)_4$ and $VOCd(Etxant)_4$ correspond to the usual one unpaired electron⁶. The dioxouranium and other bimetallic compounds are diamagnetic as expected.

The electronic spectral bands for a series of dithiocarbamate complexes of oxovanadium(II) have

Synthesis and Structural Studies on Heterobimetallic Tetrakisxanthates

R. C. AGGARWAL*, NANHAI SINGH and SUNITA SINGH
Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University,
Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 22 July 1983, revised 8 September 1986,
accepted 30 October 1986

In previous papers^{1,2}, we reported the synthesis and characterisation of bimetallic xanthates of the type $MM'(Etxant)_4$, where, $M = Co^{II}$ or Ni^{II} ; $M' = Zn^{II}$ or Cd^{II} ; $Etxant = ethyl \ xanthate$, and their complexes with Lewis bases. Formation of heterobimetallic tetraxanthates in which one of the metal ion is Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} and the other is Ag^I , Tl^I , Pb^{II} , VO^{II} or UO_2^{II} are not known so far. Synthesis and structural studies of these complexes were therefore undertaken and the results of the investigation are reported in the present paper.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF $MM'(Etxant)_4$

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
			M	M'	S
$VOZn(Etxant)_4$	Bluish green	>250	8.00 (8.27)	10.40 (10.60)	41.52 (41.76)
$VOCd(Etxant)_4$	Bluish green	170	7.55 (7.70)	16.56 (16.96)	38.52 (38.78)
$UO_2Zn(Etxant)_4$	Bright yellow	140	28.95 (29.06)	7.72 (7.96)	31.20 (31.37)
$UO_2Cd(Etxant)_4$	Bright yellow	>250	27.30 (27.50)	12.84 (12.97)	29.42 (29.66)
$PbZn(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	122	27.20 (27.50)	8.48 (8.63)	33.70 (33.99)
$PbCd(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	142	25.46 (25.87)	13.84 (14.00)	31.68 (32.00)
$Ag_2Zn(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	153	28.05 (28.34)	8.18 (8.53)	33.65 (33.95)
$Ag_2Cd(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	124	26.32 (26.69)	13.71 (13.84)	31.42 (31.64)
$Tl_2Zn(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	>250	42.46 (42.83)	6.20 (6.18)	26.39 (26.83)
$Tl_2Cd(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	144	40.28 (40.75)	10.92 (11.18)	25.27 (25.57)

been assigned using molecular orbital scheme which involves equatorial bonding as suggested by Selbin⁷ and accordingly McCormick⁸ assigned the d-d absorption bands at 16 000–16 500, 17 600–18 200 and 22 500–22 800 cm^{-1} to $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$, $b_2 \rightarrow e\pi^*$ and $b_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ transitions, respectively. The bands observed in the region 10 700–10 800, 15 200–16 000 and 18 200–18 700 cm^{-1} in the present bimetallic compounds are accordingly assigned to $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$, $b_2 \rightarrow e\pi^*$ and $b_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$, respectively, assuming tetragonal pyramidal geometry (C_{4v} symmetry) around oxovanadium(II) ion.

Ir spectra: The bands occurring in the ir spectra of $\text{MM}'(\text{Etxant})_4$ at 1 190–1 260 and 1 005–1 030 cm^{-1} are assigned^{1,2} to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ modes, respectively. The number and positions of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ indicate uninegative bidentate¹¹ behaviour of xanthate ion in the above complexes. In oxovanadium(II) complexes the V=O stretching frequency occurs at 950–990 cm^{-1} which is the usual range for such complexes⁶. The ir spectra of uranyl complexes show bands at 890–905 cm^{-1} due to asymmetric vibration of linear O—U—O group¹². In all the complexes the bands occurring below 400 cm^{-1} have been tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ modes^{13,14}, the lower one may be due to Ag—S, Tl—S, Pb—S or U—S and the higher one due to V—S, Zn—S or Cd—S stretching modes, respectively.

Based on analytical data and physicochemical studies polymeric structures are proposed for the complexes.

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Equilibrium Study of the Complex Formation of some Bivalent Metal Ions with *N*-(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-aminobiphenyl and *N*-(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine

P. P. SANGODKAR and M. S. MAYADEO*

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College, Matunga, Bombay-400 019

Manuscript received 6 September 1985, revised 6 August 1986, accepted 30 October 1986

THE literature survey reveals that no work on the interaction of the Schiff base ligands *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-aminobiphenyl (hereafter, AH) and *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine (hereafter, BH) with metal ions in solution has been reported so far. The present investigation is aimed at determination of stability constants of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Mg^{II} complexes with the ligands AH and BH in 75% (v/v) dioxan—water medium having a constant ionic strength 0.1 *M* at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Experimental

The ligands AH and BH were synthesised¹ by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde with 2-aminobiphenyl and 1-naphthylamine, respectively, in ethanol. The products were purified by repeated crystallisation from ethanol, and the purity was tested by tlc and elemental analysis: AH, m.p. 98° (Found: C, 80.00; H, 5.72; N, 4.64. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for: C, 79.21; H, 5.61; N, 4.62%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 600 (OH) and 1 605 cm^{-1} (C=N); BH, m.p. 91° (Found: C, 78.01; H, 5.53; N, 5.10. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for: C, 77.98; H, 5.42; N, 5.53%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 600 (OH) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N).

A Elico LI-15 pH meter (accuracy 0.1 pH) was employed for pH determination. The pH meter was calibrated by using aqueous buffer solutions of 0.05 *M* potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH 4.019 at 30°) and 0.01 *M* borax (pH 9.18 at 30°).

The relation between the pH meter reading (*B*) in water—dioxan medium and stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration of the same has been studied by Van Uitert and Haas² in mixtures of different compositions at different ionic strengths, and it has been shown that

$$-\log H = B + \log f + \log U^0 H$$

where, *f* is the activity coefficient of the hydrogen ions in the solvent mixture under consideration at the same temperature and ionic strength, and $U^0 H$ is the correction factor of zero ionic strength, which depends upon the composition of the solvent and temperature only.

The metal perchlorate solutions were standardised by EDTA methods³. Procedure for pH-metric